

MEETING LAB – AIHC
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Chairman Paper

“Ethics and Practice in the Human Tech approach The methodological evolution of Health Coaching”

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Abstract

At the National Assembly of Members of the Italian Health Coaching Association (AIHC) in Rome, 15th April 2023, the new Trends were addressed within some Thematic Tables. Three critical points of development have emerged: the entry into the field of Health Coaching, its self-determination, its possible social and/or socio-health role. Urged AIHC to enter the healthcare field more decisively, overcoming our natural modesty and prudence, taking on the responsibility of presenting ourselves more strongly and clearly as Wellbeing professionals. This is to give professional and qualified support from one hand to a healthcare provider in difficulty, on the other hand to a new model of Personal and Organizational Wellbeing, in a VUCA scenario. Our research on the basis of the identity of Health Coaching (Patania, Turin 2022) offers clarity, delimits and strongly accredits the identity of the Health Coach and the Wellbeing operator. The reflection on the nature of Health Coaching is now internationally shared (Patania, NEU - 2023). The fact of having this nature well defined today, having outlined its profile, having given an even greater reason to the techniques, to the humanistic approach of such a transversal association, allows us to make the intention and the setting more aligned and compact. It is here that the necessary strength emerges for such a strong awareness that it becomes lucid self-determination in order to face the challenges of new trends and the Human Tech approach in a methodologically appropriate and effective way. Thanks to the evidence developed and the creative discussion carried out within the association, including in internal training webinars, today we can present one of the first practical applications of Fromm's Objective Humanistic Ethics: the evolution of the phases of the Health Coaching session.

According to a systemic approach of social philosophy, the type of ethical commitment of Health Coaching today goes far beyond the simple guarantee of respect and safety for the client (Iordanou et al., 2017). This fact can constitute the opportunity for a meeting point between science and philosophy in finding the right balance in the methodological interpretation of the Wellbeing issue (Mitchell and Alexandrova, 2021). Instead it becomes a specific humanistic ethical action, which through the various techniques of the associates, incisively interprets its role in defence of the individual. AIHC has its strongest mission in this: to give method and substance to every interaction of the associated professionals with their clients (AIHC - see web). It is the new nascent intention that becomes a specific action to support the patient, the healthcare worker, the company. The

approach of an objective humanistic ethics in action (Fromm, 1947) provides answers in several areas. The three main areas of applied interest are:

- well-being problems in relation to moral distress and burnout (Rushton, 2006);
- the increasingly painful question of the Performance-Wellbeing balance (Peccei and van der Vorde, 2019);
- the integration of the person with the algorithm and Artificial Intelligence, in line with the Digital Humanism principles (Vienna Manifesto on Digital Humanism, 2019).

Digital humanism is already a contemporary reality. Only a few months ago in 2022 an open access publication was released to seal the European cultural movement of the same name born in Vienna. A new phase of research has opened which has brought us into contact with a nascent movement of international neo-humanism (Nida-Rümelin and Weidenfeld, 2022)..

In this Meeting Lab we'll address these topics presenting the pragmatic effects of Fromm's Ethics in our practice, accrediting its contents to Humanistic experts and researchers.

In a historical period in which transformation is the only resource that will allow individuals and communities to adapt, coaching is at the center of an epochal challenge against prejudice and against time (Eisler et al, 2013). We need to be well centered on ourselves and in observing our client we must be able to clearly see the relationship between his being, his expectations and above all the social pressures to which he is subjected (Fromm, 1961). In attempting to generate well-being, the health coach tries to help his client not only to overcome his own limiting beliefs, but also to defend himself from ambiguities and false expectations. The more the Wellbeing Practitioner knows who he is, the more his support will determine his effectiveness in the speed of transformation (ICF Embodies the Coaching Mindset – see web). Knowing what the qualities of being poses a new way of implementing transformation (Fromm, 1976).

The main applications of a humanistic culture of ethics, and in particular in the conflict of values, mainly concern moral distress. As Erich Fromm well described, in the difficult conditions that prelude illness, moral conflict is the result of moral loneliness (Fromm, 1947). Today the individual often find himself in the position of facing moral dilemmas that block him in a state of frustration, which affects his well-being (Valdesolo and De Steno, 2006). Humanistic-inspired Health Coaching can intervene effectively in these cases, for example by helping its client to make a detailed analysis of the values at stake and the related moral rules. By knowing the social dynamics in which the patient or caregiver finds themselves, the Wellness Operator or Health Coach can interact effectively with their partner, avoiding being unaware victims of contingent moral ambiguities (Valdesolo and De Steno, 2007).

The distortion of social phenomena is such that certain behaviors, although definable as "normal" from a statistical point of view (central part of the Gaussian curve of the population), in reality cannot be truly correlated to a "natural" behavior of the person in the achievement of their well-being and of one's human nature (Fromm, 1947). This failure to achieve is often related to a personal moral failure, related to the value system and ethics. Frommian ethics promotes the use of reason as a solution, as a guiding tool of practical rationality, as an alternative to intelligence. This is consistent both with Aristotelian "phronesis" (Risari, 2017) and with the empirical approach of Health Coaching. This explains the pragmatic usefulness of Fromm's thought in perfecting the use of professional empowerment techniques and also explains how many of these techniques work on value alignment, that is, on the resolution of moral conflict.

A practical example of such conflicts is the phenomenon of moral distress and burnout. The healthcare worker finds himself conditioned by the current implicit and undeclared morality, which leads him into a condition of value conflict: he often wants to provide assistance to the patient and is not able to do so, due to lack of time, facilities and means (Mealer and Moss, 2016). This stress turns out to be dysfunctional with respect to the natural interest in developing personal potential. To the point of overshadowing one's own profound interest, the art of living and preserving one's own well-being (Fromm, 1961).

As can be seen, both towards the organization and towards clinical duty, personal values come into play. Knowing these mechanisms in depth allows all the actors in the scenario to calibrate their respective expectations to create a new sustainable scenario. Without this awareness, provided by Fromm's model of social criticism, any attempt risks unbalancing the system in one direction or another, generating conflicts or polarization, in the creation of a dialectic between man and society (Fromm, 1961). For these reasons, the issue of Wellbeing, in fact, is closely related to humanistic ethics in a socially pragmatic and objective sense (Fromm, 1947)(Bocean et al. 2022)(Patania, Medmagazine 2023).

An example of a practical application of Health Coaching on moral distress, or burn out, is to use the 4A system: Ask, Affirm, Assess, Act (AACN, 2020). It is a scheme that offers a model of interaction of the health worker with his system of reference, and can be the subject of a health coaching session. The main point where the difference can be made is undoubtedly the first: ASK. It concerns the ability to understand the state of incipient difficulty of the caregiver, who becomes aware of his own condition and moral dilemma. Here only a Health Coach with a clear idea of the dynamics of values, ethics and social interaction can best understand the client's responses. So you can help him with further questions to explore his own moral question in depth. Thanks to this precision, you can take the next step, that of AFFIRM your condition and your will to act in taking care of yourself. The assessment of the discomfort will also be simpler (ASSESS) and the final action plan will be more effective (ACT). A classic coaching approach, being two-dimensional, lacks this depth (Patania, Berlin 2023). The interference encountered in the past by Health Coaches or Wellness Operators in developing their support was linked precisely to this deficiency. I return to what I underlined at the beginning of our dialogue: *knowing how to be, leads to knowing how to do*. Having found the roots of the Health Coaching identity allows us to address the thorniest difficulties encountered within the world of Wellbeing in a more resolute and systemic way. Thanks to this approach, the Health Coach can truly take the field with determination in the healthcare sector and for this reason needs an upgraded session model.

The model proposed by humanistic ethics contemplates man's natural drive (therefore defined as objective) towards his own self-realization. The most convinced humanists go so far as to say that this is a natural drive towards joy. According with a comment of Julia Chi Taylor, "*Accepting the belief that all beings want to grow and move into alignment, it is possible to bring our stories into conscious awareness, and we are able to experience a different reality to the one we believed*"

about the book of the evolutionary coaching master, Richard Barrett (Barrett, 2012). Today a Health Coach must know how to balance between his client's drive towards self-realization and that given by his need to relate to others. Environments are important for the individual, and in their balance lies the secret of personal growth, one's professional maturity and one's psycho-physical well-being. There are various tools developed within this thought pattern, one of many is Von Thun's development square, based precisely on the balancing of ethical-value dilemmas, with the aim of avoiding the excesses of useless and harmful overcompensation (see web, Von Thun, 1989). All this evidence leads to a single point of synthesis: it is extremely important to deeply explore the ethical aspects of the world of the person's internal and external values, in order to support them and develop their potential in the most natural and functional way, exactly as Fromm described in his text "A Man for Himself".

If we observe the classic executive coaching model, *intelligence driven*, this will mainly focus on forcing the person's choice based on the pressures he receives, implementing problem solving, measuring the objective, its definition and the available resources.

WHAT? > HOW? > TARGET > PAIN > WHY? > WHAT 2? > HOW 2? > TARGET 2

In this classic coaching session approach, it is assumed, in a non-judgmental way, that the person has valid reference values taken for granted. This is where the error lies, which is usually corrected later. The most pressing values on the person lead him and the coach to build an action plan on a first objective which is usually self-sabotaged by the client, generating pain and frustration. Then the coach runs for cover, looking for other alternative goals that are "really" important to the person. Ultimately, it takes place through trial and error, and learning occurs in a superficial and not completely conscious way, furthermore with a waste of time and emotional energy. The flow starts from the question "What?" (What do you want to achieve right now?) Then we move on to "How?" (How can you achieve this?). Only after failing does the "Why?" it may or may not emerge in awareness, or be unconsciously encouraged to guide the person towards a new Target 2 that is more appropriate and in line with one's value systems, even if internal conflicts might come up, due to the internalization of unresolved external conditioning values.

A Health Coach has the person's well-being as his first duty, therefore the approach must necessarily be different and consider the risk of pain and frustration of self-sabotage. Furthermore, it is unthinkable for a Health Coach to take the setting and current condition of his client for granted, especially if he is in a state of suffering. It is his duty to go in depth in the first sessions, challenging the beliefs generated in the person by anonymous authority (Fromm, 1961) and even giving up an action plan, at least until the person's value system has been purified and balanced. The Why? it comes first, as the primary condition of the person's sense of purpose. This is what will guide healthy awareness and generate beneficial targets, which will lead to the state of Flow (Csikszentmihályi, 1990), self-realization and Wellbeing.

What makes this *reason-driven* approach effective from a Health Coaching point of view is the first phase of normalization of the person's reference pattern of values, which is concentrated at the core. This liberation from external conditioning allows the client to consciously leave with a well-defined "Why?", a clear sense of purpose (Dolan, 2006).

This will generate autotelic activities of Flow and Wellbeing, avoiding the risk of self-sabotage and consequent suffering. On the other hand, for the Health Coach, it will be important to raise the level of comparison from two-dimensional *intelligence* to the deep and three-dimensional plane of *reason* and systemic critical thinking. This also includes, always in line with the ICF competencies of the Coaching Mindset, also considering in the relationship the interference given by the anonymous authority of one's own value system and one's history and background. In this specification, we must understand, as well stated by Fromm, that *reason CONTAINS intelligence*, and adds to it the sense of purpose. Therefore, by including it, it receives all the pragmatic elements. Unlike this, while intelligence is cognitive and must necessarily be able to take action in tactical problem solving, reason can both operate effectively in this sense and pause and go deeper.

Reason is the master of both fast and slow thinking (Kahneman, 2013).

This new session setting will involve developing specific skills in the world of values, referring to authors such as Barrett (2014), Dilts (2012) and Dolan (2020), just to name a few. According with these authors, all this will produce greater efficiency of the system, with more focus, less dispersion of emotional energy, self-generation of positive energy and achievement of more goals in the same period of time considered (Target 1 and Target 2 in the figure).

Finally, values are important components of a person's motivation and must be deeply understood in order to help the individual make the most ethically respectful and functional choice towards the development of personal potential and Well-being.

This kind of balance is even more necessary in an accelerated and complex society, where the functional deceleration of coaching can allow the person to effectively resonate with social phenomena (Rosa, 2021). The solution of the Human Tech duo expects man to do his best, both in conceiving and in giving meaning to technological progress.

In conclusion, based on the evidence of our research, the Health Coach, more than any other, helps his client starting from a true, profound sense of purpose. It helps to dig deep into the natural whys of the person, before starting with any exploration of possibilities and opportunities. What distinguishes the classic approach of EXECUTIVE COACHING (EC) from HEALTH COACHING (HC) can be described according to some polarities:

EC moves towards OBJECTIVES > HC seeks PURPOSE
 EC is based on REPETITION > HC is based on NARRATION
 EC is EGO coaching > HC is coaching of the SELF

to put it with Fromm and Saint Thomas Aquinas, respectively:

- EC is motivated to DO (intelligence)
- HC is motivated by BEING in DOING/not DOING (reason)

“*Agere Sequitur Esse*”

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